

ACTIVATION OF ATP-DEPENDENT POTASSIUM CHANNELS AS A DIRECTION OF PHARMACOLOGICAL CORRECTION OF TOXIC KIDNEY DAMAGE**Filpets N.***Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
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Department of Nervous diseases, Psychiatry and Medical Psychology named after S.M. Savenko***ABSTRACT**

The relevance of research on the pharmacological regulation of the activity of ATP-dependent potassium (KATP) channels is driven by functional versatility of channels of this type. Their participation in body adaptation reactions, physiological and pathological processes stimulate the search and development of new drugs - modulators of KATP channels. In this experimental study, we focused on the renal action of the fluorine-containing activator of KATP channels flocalin and changes in the homeostatic processes of the kidneys under its influence. The obtained results indicate that the renal effects of flocalin in laboratory white rats with toxic kidney damage by sublimate are characterized by diuretic and antiproteinuric effects, a decrease in retention azotemia, an increase in the rate of glomerular filtration and reabsorption of sodium ions in the tubular part of the nephron. The research results indicate the participation of KATP channels in the development of toxic nephropathy and the protective effects of flocalin, both in the glomerular and tubular parts of the nephron.

Keywords: ATP-dependent potassium channels, pharmacological activation, flocalin, toxic nephropathy, kidney functions and processes.

An important pharmacological characteristic of drugs is the ability to support the mechanisms of regulation of the functional state of organs and systems and to directly protect cells under conditions of damage to the body. Such properties are inherent in the class of ion channel modulators. Ion channels play a critical role in various physiological and pathological processes, making them attractive targets for the development of drugs for diseases such as coronary heart disease, hypertension, diabetes, epilepsy, cancer, and chronic pain [1, 2].

In fact, violation of the ratio of ions, in particular, in which the intracellular concentration of calcium ions increases, cause endothelial dysfunction, vasoconstriction, disruption of oxidative processes, inhibition of tissue respiration, lead to cell apoptosis or their necrosis. In addition to calcium channel blockers, pharmacological KATP channel activators, which include flocalin, protect against calcium overload. The received scientifically confirmed information [3, 4] about the high antispasmodic activity of flocalin, vasodilatory effects, the presence of a number of different cardioprotective mechanisms testify to the multifaceted pharmacodynamics of the promising drug and confirm the relevance of continuing research into its pharmacotherapeutic properties.

Taking into account the dependence of renal processes on the integrative functioning of potassium channels of vessels, cells of the juxtaglomerular apparatus, tubules and collecting tubules, as well as the important role of ion channels in the mechanisms underlying proteinuria [5, 6], we studied the renal effects of flocalin under conditions of hyperhydration of organism of laboratory white rats. Based on the fact that the

drug increases diuresis, exerts a natriuretic effect, activates glomerular filtration, affects the acid regulatory function of the kidneys when the volume of extracellular fluid in the body increases [7, 8], the question of the renal effect of flocalin in experimental toxic damage to the kidneys is of interest.

The aim of the research was to assess the state of renal processes after pharmacological activation of KATP-dependent potassium channels in rats with sublimate nephropathy and to find out the therapeutic possibilities of flocalin under the conditions of the development of tubulo-interstitial disintegration.

Materials and methods. Experiments were conducted on laboratory white rats weighing 0.15-0.17 kg, which were kept on a hyposodium diet (wheat grain) with free access to settled tap water. Sublimate was administered once intraperitoneally at a dose of 5 mg/kg of body weight. Two hours later, a group of rats with nephropathy was intragastrically injected with Flocalin at a dose of 5 mg/kg per 1% starch mucus in a volume of 5 ml/kg body weight. Control rats were similarly injected with a starch suspension. After 30 min, all rats were water-stressed by intragastric administration of tap water (50 ml/kg) and placed in individual exchange cages for urine collection for 2 hours. Rats were euthanized under nembutal anesthesia (1% sodium ethaminal solution, dose 20 mg/kg), following the provisions of the "European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes" (Strasbourg, 1986). The content of sodium ions in urine and blood plasma was determined by the method of flame photometry on FPL-1. Creatinine concentration in urine was determined according to Folin's method, in blood plasma - according to Popper's method in Merzon's modification

[9]. Protein in urine was determined by reaction with sulfosalicylic acid. Indicators were calculated according to generally accepted formulas for evaluating kidney functions and processes [10]. Statistical processing was carried out using the computer program "Statgraphics". Reliability was determined by Student's t-test.

Results and discussion. The obtained experimental data on changes in the functional state of the kidneys on the classical model of sublimate damage to

the kidneys (Table 1) indicate the development of a pathological process characteristic of toxic nephropathies [11]. Thus, the initial period of the formation of renal failure was characterized by a decrease in diuresis, the development of retention azotemia with an increase in the concentration of creatinine in the blood plasma. The concentration of protein in the urine increased and proteinuria occurred. There was a decrease in the reabsorption of sodium ions in the renal tubules.

Table 1

Changes in the functional state of the kidneys in rats at the initial stage of sublimate nephropathy after a single injection of Flocalin, $\bar{x} \pm S_x$

Indicators	Control (n=6)	Sublimate nephropathy (n=6)	Sublimate nephropathy and Flocalin (n=6)
Diuresis, ml/2h/100g	3.5±0.52	2.0±0.20*	3.1±0.12**
Creatinine concentration in blood plasma, $\mu\text{mol/l}$	39.5±2.75	55.7±0.33*	43.5±2.5**
Glomerular filtration rate, $\mu\text{l/min}$	390.5±70.30	303.7±30.30	602.4±56.89* **
Protein concentration, g/l	0.005±0.0017	0.04±0.008*	0.01±0.004**
Protein excretion, mg/2h	0.02±0.007	0.09±0.013*	0.03±0.012**
Protein excretion, mg/100 μl of glomerular filtrate	0.005±0.0018	0.03±0.006*	0.006±0.0020**
Excretion of sodium ions, $\mu\text{mol/2 h}$	1.02±0.25	0.39±0.062*	1.22±0.32**
Proximal reabsorption of sodium ions, mmol/2h	5.5±0.88	4.8±0.52	7.9±0.66* **
Distal reabsorption of sodium ions, $\mu\text{mol/2 h}$	457.0±70.69	277.6±30.11*	367.3±27.18**

* - reliability compared to control indicators ($p < 0.05$); ** - probability compared to the indicators of sulemic nephropathy ($p < 0.05$).

Administration of Flocalin 2 hours after simulation of sublimate nephropathy led to an increase in diuresis and natriuresis. The regulatory role of membrane KATP channels consists in eliminating the activation of vasoconstrictor effects under the conditions of the development of toxic nephropathy, characterized by an increased rate of glomerular filtration and a decrease in plasma creatinine. An increase in the intensity of renal blood flow and the membrane-stabilizing effect of Flocalin are reflected by a change in the permeability of the pores of the glomerular membrane, which prevents the penetration of macromolecules into the mesangial space. The concentration of protein in the urine decreased, the protein excretion indicators reached control values, which is also associated with the improvement of the functional state of the glomerulus, as well as the tubular, mostly proximal, part of the nephron. The tubuloprotective properties of Flocalin are also evidenced by the increase in the transtubular transport of sodium ions in both the proximal and distal tubules of the kidneys.

Conclusions. The effect of Flocalin under the conditions of the development of sublimate nephropathy is characterized by an increase in the rate of glomerular filtration and tubular reabsorption of sodium ions, activation of the water-regulatory and excretory functions of the kidneys, and an antiproteinuric effect. The regulatory effect of Flocalin on the main renal processes confirms the ability of Flocalin to reproduce the biological mechanisms of protection of ATP-dependent potassium channels and expands its pharmacodynamics.

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